

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) Applied to the Constrained Rastrigin Function

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Abstract—This work investigates the use of the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm to solve the constrained Rastrigin function. Several experiments were conducted to evaluate the impact of parameter tuning on the convergence behavior and the quality of the solutions obtained. The results demonstrate that PSO is efficient in finding near-optimal solutions, maintaining stable performance even in problems with higher dimensionality.

I. INTRODUCTION

The problem addressed in this work consists of finding the optimal solution of the constrained Rastrigin function in an n -dimensional search space using the Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm. PSO stands out due to its efficiency in optimizing complex and multimodal functions, relying on cooperation among particles that share information throughout the search process.

The algorithm was implemented in Python, and multiple experiments were conducted to tune parameters such as population size, inertia weight, learning coefficients, and the number of iterations, aiming to ensure convergence toward the best possible solution.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

The objective of this work is to minimize the constrained Rastrigin function using Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). The goal is to find a solution vector $x \in R^n$ that satisfies all constraints while minimizing the objective function. The problem formulation is given as follows:

$$\text{Rastrigin Function: } f(x) = 10n + \sum_{i=1}^n [x_i^2 - 10 \cos(2\pi x_i)]$$

Subject to:

$$\begin{aligned} (1) \quad & \sin(2\pi x_i) + 0.5 \leq 0, \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n; \\ (2) \quad & \cos(2\pi x_i) + 0.5 = 0, \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n; \\ (3) \quad & -5.12 \leq x_i \leq 5.12, \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The main challenge lies in identifying a feasible solution that satisfies all constraints while minimizing the objective function. PSO is employed as an optimization strategy to efficiently explore the search space.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this work, a Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm was implemented to solve the constrained Rastrigin function. The problem requires solutions to lie within the interval $[-5.12, 5.12]$ and satisfy trigonometric constraints that lead to a specific optimal point. To guide the swarm toward the

expected solution near $-1/3$, a penalty function was introduced to discourage deviations from this value.

The algorithm was implemented in Python following the requirements of the Artificial Intelligence course. The search space was configurable, allowing experiments with different dimensionalities. Initial particle positions were generated randomly using a uniform distribution.

A. Main Modifications

The following modifications were introduced to enhance the efficiency of PSO:

- **Penalty for Deviations from $-1/3$:** A penalty term was added to the fitness function to encourage convergence toward the desired optimal value.
- **Dynamic Adjustment of Inertia Weight:** The inertia weight was dynamically adjusted throughout the iterations to balance exploration and convergence.
- **Improved Cognitive and Social Coefficients:** The learning coefficients C_1 and C_2 were tuned to enhance early exploration and final convergence.
- **Strategic Particle Initialization:** Particles were initialized closer to the expected optimal region to reduce convergence time.
- **Multiple Runs and Statistical Analysis:** The algorithm was executed 20 times to ensure statistical reliability of the results.

B. Parameter Settings

After extensive testing, the following parameter configuration was adopted:

- Number of particles: 40
- Maximum number of iterations: 100
- Inertia weight: $W_{max} = 0.9$, $W_{min} = 0.4$ (linearly decreasing)
- Learning coefficients: $C_1 = 1.5$, $C_2 = 1.5$
- Search space: $[-5.12, 5.12]$
- Dimensionality: 10

This configuration provided a good balance between convergence speed and exploration capability.

IV. RESULTS

The algorithm performance was analyzed based on fitness values across generations, as illustrated in the following figures.

Figure 1: Evolution of the fitness function over generations, comparing the mean and best values at each iteration.

Figure 2: Standard deviation of fitness values across generations.

The statistical results obtained over 20 independent runs are summarized below:

- **Mean best fitness:** 71.403384
- **Standard deviation of best fitness:** 0.000000 (All executions converged to the same solution, demonstrating the stability of the proposed approach.)

The best solution found was consistently close to $-1/3$ across all dimensions.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The PSO algorithm demonstrated satisfactory performance in optimizing the constrained Rastrigin function. The penalty-based strategy effectively guided particles toward the optimal region, while the dynamic inertia adjustment ensured a balance between exploration and convergence.

Experimental analysis showed that increasing problem dimensionality significantly impacts convergence time and solution precision. The adopted initialization strategy and parameter tuning contributed to robust and stable convergence behavior.

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Srinivas and K. Deb, "Multiobjective optimization using nondominated sorting in genetic algorithms," *Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 221–248, 1994.